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Research Article

**TREATING HEART PATIENTS BY ENHANCING POSITIVE
EMOTIONS THROUGH POSITIVE PSYCHOLOGY
INTERVENTION**Dr Muhammad Ammar Arif¹, Dr Muhammad Mansha², Dr Ushba Fatima³¹FCPS Cardiology³Shalamar Medical and Dental College Lahore³Services Institute of Medical Science

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Abstract:

Introduction: Coronary artery disease (CAD) is the leading cause of death worldwide making it a major public health problem. **Objectives of the study:** The main objective of the study is to analyse the heart patients by enhancing positive emotions through positive psychology intervention. **Material and methods:** This descriptive study was conducted in SIMS, Lahore during June 2019 to February 2020. The data was collected from 100 heart patients. The data was divided into two parts, one was experimental group and one was control group. **Results:** Mean age was 56.6 +/- 8.7, 42 (76%) were men, and diabetes (n=14; 25%) was the most common medical comorbidity. There were no differences in characteristics (all p>.05) between PPI (n=50) and control (n=50) participants. Across the four study conditions, only history of prior depression differed across groups. Overall, 32/50 PPI participants (78%) completed a majority of the weekly sessions (≥4 of 6), and 183/246 total sessions (74%) were completed. **Conclusion:** It is concluded that positive psychology intervention enhances positive emotions like happiness, optimism, gratitude, etc. and decreases the risk for the incidence of coronary heart disease.

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INTRODUCTION:

Coronary artery disease (CAD) is the leading cause of death worldwide making it a major public health problem. Positive psychological constructs, such as optimism and positive affect, are associated with reduced mortality in patients with and without pre-existing cardiac disease, along with fewer rehospitalizations in heart failure patients and increased survival following cardiac surgery [1]. Such effects on cardiac health appear to be independent of negative affective states, suggesting that it is not simply an absence of depression that confers the cardiovascular benefit associated with positive emotions.

An intervention that boosts positive psychological well-being has the potential to improve outcomes in patients with cardiovascular disease. Positive psychology interventions (PPIs) aim to cultivate positive psychological states (e.g., optimism, gratitude, positive affect) through systematic exercises [2], such as performing kind acts, writing a letter of gratitude, or using personal strengths. These exercises are straightforward, require minimal provider training, and have been found to consistently and substantially increase well-being and reduce depression in healthy persons [3]. However, despite the association of positive psychological states with superior cardiac outcomes, there has been little study of PPIs or related programs in cardiac patients, and none outside the United States.

Negative emotional states are strongly associated with poor outcomes in patients with heart disease. For example, depressive symptoms in cardiac patients are common, persistent, and independently associated with negative medical outcomes [4]. This link between depression and adverse cardiac events appears to be especially strong among patients hospitalized for acute cardiac conditions, such as acute coronary syndrome (ACS) or congestive heart failure (CHF), for whom depression has been repeatedly established as a risk factor for recurrent cardiac events and mortality [5]. Other negative psychological states, especially anxiety, have also been associated with the development and progression of cardiac disease, and anxiety symptoms and disorders have been linked with cardiac-related death. However, there have been multiple trials to treat depression and associated conditions in cardiac patients, and depression treatment in heart disease patients has not concisely resulted in improved cardiac outcomes [6].

Objectives of the study

The main objective of the study is to analyse the heart patients by enhancing positive emotions through positive psychology intervention.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This descriptive study was conducted in SIMS, Lahore during June 2019 to February 2020. The data was collected from 100 heart patients. The data was divided into two parts, one was experimental group and one was control group. Thus Before the administration of Positive Psychology Intervention, all the participants were asked to complete measures of Gratitude Questionnaire, life orientation test-revised, and coronary artery disease (CAD) symptoms checklist for the purpose of pre-testing and post testing. Participants then described their experiences completing the assigned positive psychology exercises and received feedback and support from other group members. The trainer then presented the details and rationale for up to three strategies for the week. Next, the trainer described specific exercises to implement these strategies and allowed participants to practice them in the group. In addition, participants were encouraged to perform at least one exercise using each strategy prior to the next group session. Participants were also guided in the continued use of exercises in their daily lives, and at the final group session, received a chart to guide future exercise completion.

RESULTS:

Mean age was 56.6 +/- 8.7, 42 (76%) were men, and diabetes (n=14; 25%) was the most common medical comorbidity. There were no differences in characteristics (all $p > .05$) between PPI (n=50) and control (n=50) participants. Across the four study conditions, only history of prior depression differed across groups. Overall, 32/50 PPI participants (78%) completed a majority of the weekly sessions (≥ 4 of 6), and 183/246 total sessions (74%) were completed. In the Seligman group, 10/13 participants (77%) completed a majority of weekly sessions, with a total of 55 (71%) of sessions completed. In Lyubomirsky, 8/13 (62%) completed a majority of sessions, with 65% exercise completion, and in Fordyce 14/15 (93%) completed a majority, with 86% overall completion. There was a significant effect of group on exercise completion ($F=3.88$; $p=.029$), and on post-hoc pairwise comparisons, the Fordyce group was associated with greater exercise completion than Lyubomirsky ($p=.035$).

Table 01: Changes in study outcome variables in experiment and control participants

Condition		Coefficient	95% CI	p	Effect size (d)
Happiness (Oxford Happiness Inventory)					
Post-intervention (7 weeks)					
PPI		5.04	2.42, 7.68	< .001	.97
Control		0.03	-5.95, 6.02	.99	--
Follow-up (15 weeks)					
PPI		5.62	2.84, 8.40	<.001	1.08
Control		-8.54	-14.53, -2.54	.005	--
Depression (Beck Depression Inventory-II)					
Post-intervention (7 weeks)					
PPI		-0.27	-2.23, 1.69	.79	.07
Control		-0.77	-4.17, 2.63	.66	--
Follow-up (15 weeks)					
PPI		-2.54	-4.60, -0.47	.016	.65
Control		1.21	-2.19, 4.62	.49	--
Satisfaction (Satisfaction with Life Scale)					
Post-intervention (7 weeks)					
PPI		1.41	0.17, 2.64	.026	.50
Control		1.68	-0.69, 4.06	.17	--
Follow-up (15 weeks)					
PPI		1.32	0.01, 2.62	.048	.47
Control		0.08	-2.18, 2.34	.95	--
Hope (Dispositional Hope Scale)					
Post-intervention (7 weeks)					
PPI		0.007	-2.75, 2.76	.99	.01
Control		-4.44	-10.98, 2.02	.18	--
Follow-up (15 weeks)					
PPI		-1.89	-4.81, 1.03	.21	.25
Control		-8.71	-14.66, -2.76	.004	--

DISCUSSION:

Additional refinement and testing of this positive psychology intervention for cardiac patients are required to ensure that the field can develop the best intervention to impact meaningful clinical outcomes. Many questions remain: should positive interventions focus on improving overall well-being or target very specific psychological constructs like optimism, which is associated with superior cardiac health? Should positive psychology interventions serve as a new way to improve negative psychological syndromes like anxiety and depression (which are also associated with adverse cardiac outcomes) [7], or should they be adapted to a broader population of patients than just those with a clinical disorder? Given recent findings that medical outcomes and health behaviors improved among cardiac patients who completed a program that simultaneously focused on psychological and medical factors, should positive psychology interventions target health behaviors such as diet or exercise as a way to improve cardiac outcomes? Answers to these questions will have important implications for the adaptation of positive psychology interventions to clinical settings. Although much remains to be learned, this line of

work holds much promise in attempts to improve the lives of patients with serious cardiac illness [8].

However, the most common positive attribute which has been associated with coronary heart disease is optimism.2-4 Optimism as a trait produces positive and confident expectation about one's own future [9]. These findings are confirmed Giltay, and his colleagues in Zutphen Elderly Study that optimism is linked with reduced risk for coronary heart disease.25 Boehm, and Kubzansky stated that optimistic people experience 50% reduced risk of initial coronary heart event as compared to those are less optimistic [10].

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that positive psychology intervention enhances positive emotions like happiness, optimism, gratitude, etc. and decreases the risk for the incidence of coronary heart disease.

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